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Advantages and prospects of distance education in Ukraine

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The development of modern technologies provides great opportunities for science and education. The basis of socio-economic development of the information society is not a material production, but the production of information and knowledge. For any country, the degree of its economic and technological development, the welfare of society is proportional to the average level of knowledge, skills, abilities and qualifications of its active population. Highly qualified people are better adapted to possible changes in the profile of work, they are less vulnerable in the cases of its loss, and they are able to update and improve their knowledge and skills. The development of high technology on an increasing scale increases the demand for intelligence in education of the broad masses of the population of any country. This radically changes the state of the education system in the society, and its institutional status. Education is becoming not only a tool for the interpenetration of knowledge and technology on a global scale, but also a capital, a means of fighting for the market, and solving geopolitical problems.

Modern society needs mass quality education that can provide increased demands on consumers and producers of material and spiritual goods. Even wealthy countries are unable to fulfill the social order of society by increasing spending on education, increasing the number of educational institutions and other traditional means. Therefore, the emergence of distance education is not accidental; it is a natural stage of development and adaptation of education to modern conditions.

All over the world, distance education exists and occupies a socially significant place in the field of education.

In recent years, the development of information technology has made the problem of modernizing the education system relevant. The essence of such modernization is most reflected in the concept of distance education (DE), which, thanks to such a global phenomenon as the Internet, covers a wide range of society and becomes a major factor in its development. Such modernization of the education system is becoming especially important in Ukraine.

DE is an open learning system that involves active communication between a teacher and a student through modern technology and multimedia. This form of education gives the freedom to choose the place, time and pace of learning.

The DE system has a number of advantages and significantly expands the range of potential students. Young people who cannot combine study with work or live in a remote area from regional centers, military men,

housewives, managers, businessmen or students wishing to study in parallel have the opportunity to receive distance education. Distance learning is suitable for almost everyone, because it allows you to combine learning and everyday life harmoniously.

It is worth noting that DE is an affordable opportunity to get an education abroad with minimal financial costs with a wide choice of specialties, as most universities in Europe and the United States have introduced such a convenient form of education for students much earlier than Ukraine.

Modern education requires continuous expansion of the perception of the complexity of the world and the formation of the information society. In order for knowledge to have a concrete connection with actions, it is necessary to constantly "teach yourself", supplementing and expanding your education. This is the goal of distance education.

Students and entrants are offered a curriculum, both in specialties and in individual courses. It is important that the student visits the campus at least once a year and participates in the face-to-face classes. Some educational institutions build the learning process on the basis of computer software. This means that the teacher and the student do not actually communicate with each other, but receive and transmit information by e-mail. Graduation documents are also sent to students by mail. In Ukraine, distance education is extremely important.

Let us note the main advantages of distance learning:

- accessibility to all segments of the population;
- no need to attend lectures and seminars;
- democratic relationship between a teacher and a student;
- complex software;
- leading educational technologies;
- individual learning process;
- flexible consultations.

The prospect and improvement of the distance learning system in Ukraine is the introduction of modern technologies in the process. Currently, the problem of distance education is being developed by almost all universities in Ukraine.

Despite the rather extensive list of positive qualities of distance education, as in any other form of education, there are several shortcomings. First of all, it is difficult to identify distance students, because at the present stage of technology development it is quite difficult to verify who is taking the exam. However, universities that provide distance learning courses have found a way out of the situation in the obligatory presence of students in several exams at the university. In this case, the provision of the identity documents is mandatory.

Among the important shortcomings of the distance form of education in Ukraine is also the lack of direct contact between the personal teacher (tutor) and the distance student due to the extreme professional workload of local teachers. Students of foreign distance courses can receive answers to their letters in a few hours, because there are many more teachers with significant experience in the implementation of DE in the countries than students. Unfortunately, the opposite situation has developed in Ukraine - we have a lot of people wishing to receive distance education, and there are few experienced teachers who are familiar with the latest technologies of distance communication.

In general, we can say that distance education for pupils, students and teachers is quite successful, and in the realities of today's world development the online education has already quite confidently taken place next to traditional one.